

On thiogalactosides : Synthesis of *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides

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Abstract : Several *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides have been synthesized by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide and arylthiocarbamides. The identities of these newly synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Galactosyl bromide, arylthiocarbamides, arylisothiocarbamides.

Recently, we have reported a method for a synthesis of *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides by the interaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide and arylthiocarbamides¹. In view of several applications of *S*-galactosylated compounds in medicinal chemistry, industries and in many other ways^{2,3}, it appeared interesting to carry out the synthesis of thiogalactosides. In the present communication seven *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides (3) have been reported. They were prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide (1) and arylthiocarbamides (2).

Results and discussion

Isopropanolic (30 ml) suspension of tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide (0.014 M, 6 g) and phenylthiocarbamide (0.014 M, 2.22 g) was heated on water bath at about 70 °C until the suspension get cleared. The clear solution was then kept at room temperature for 18 h. It was mixed with 100 ml distilled water. This aqueous solution was acidic and non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution.

The aqueous solution when basified with NH_4OH afforded a sticky mass which was not solidified on standing for several hours. It was purified by ethanol and water. It gave charring test and was non-desulphurisable. Its specific rotation was found $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 226^\circ$ (c, 1 in CHCl_3).

The IR, ^1H NMR and mass⁴⁻⁹ spectral analysis (Experimental) and elemental analysis (Table 1) clearly indicated the product and assign the structure as *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl-1-phenylisothiocarbamide (3a).

When the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide was extended to other arylthiocarbamides the related *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides (3b-g) were obtained.

Experimental

All the melting points recorded are found uncorrected. The structures of newly synthesized compounds were confirmed on the basis of elemental and spectral analysis. IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in KBr on a FTIR

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl,
(e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl
Ac = COCH_3

Scheme 1

Table 1. Interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide (0.014 *M*, 6 g) and arylthiocarbamides (0.014 *M*) in 2-propanol

Sl. no.	Aryl thiocarbamide	<i>S</i> -Tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl galactosyl 1-aryl isothiocarbamides (yield, g)	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Requires)		[α] _D ²⁷ (c, CHCl ₃)
					N	S	
1.	Phenyl (2.22)	-phenyl (3a) (1.41)	98	20.12	5.62 (5.80)	6.42 (6.63)	+226° (1.00)
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Phenyl (2.72)	- <i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl (3b) (2.5)	102	33.11	5.25 (5.42)	5.90 (6.19)	+256° (1.00)
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl (2.72)	- <i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl (3c) (1.41)	108	18.78	5.30 (5.42)	6.02 (6.19)	+137° (1.00)
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl (2.72)	- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl (3d) (1.40)	116	18.60	5.29 (5.42)	6.00 (6.19)	-204° (1.00)
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl (2.42)	- <i>o</i> -tolyl (3e) (2.76)	106	38.34	5.32 (5.64)	6.15 (6.45)	+117° (0.986)
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl (2.42)	- <i>m</i> -tolyl (3f) (1.99)	98	27.62	5.30 (5.64)	6.25 (6.45)	-59° (0.99)
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl (2.42)	- <i>p</i> -tolyl (3g) (1.68)	100	23.34	5.38 (5.64)	6.27 (6.45)	-12.12° (0.99)

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

Perkin-Elmer (4000–450 cm⁻¹) spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra are run on Bruker DRX-300 instrument operating at 300 MHz using CDCl₃ solution with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on micromass Quattro II triple quadrupole mass spectrometer and Jeol SX-102 FAB instrument. Specific rotations were recorded on digital polarimeter.

The required tetra-*O*-acetyl galactosyl bromide¹⁰ and arylthiocarbamides¹¹ were prepared by the methods described earlier.

(3a) IR (KBr) : 3449 (N–H), 1750 (C=O), 1591 (C=N), 1438 (C–N), 1229 (C–O), 1059 (C–H def. galactose unit), 768 (C–S), 913 cm⁻¹ (β-isomer of galactose); ¹H NMR δ 7.4–7.0 (5H, m, Ar–H), 6.9–6.8 (2H, s, N–H), 5.46 (1H, m, H₁), 5.38–5.09 (2H, m, H₂ and H₃), 4.13–4.05 (2H, m, H₆, H_{6'}), 4.05–4.03 (2H, m, H₄ and H₅), 2.1–1.9 (12H, m, 4-OAc group). Mass (*m/z*) 482 (M⁺), 483 (M⁺+1), 441, 407, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 52.08; H, 5.27; N, 5.62; S, 6.42. C₂₁H₂₆O₉N₂S requires : C, 52.28; H, 5.39; N, 5.80; S, 6.63%).

(3b) IR (KBr) : 3381 (N–H), 1747 (C=O), 1592 (C=N), 1437 (C–N), 1232 (C–O), 1054 (C–H def. galactose unit), 771 (C–S), 908 cm⁻¹ (β-isomer of galactose); ¹H NMR δ 7.3–6.9 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.38 (1H, s, N–H), 5.50 (1H, s, N–H), 5.47 (1H, m, H₁), 5.46–5.34 (1H, m, H₂), 5.10–4.87 (2H, m, H₂ and H₄), 4.36–4.20 (1H, m, H₅), 4.1–4.04 (2H, m, H₆ and H_{6'}), 2.1–1.2 (12H, m, 4-OAc). Mass (*m/z*) 516 (M⁺), 474, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 48.61; H, 4.59; N, 5.25; S, 5.92. C₂₁H₂₅O₉N₂S requires : C, 48.83; H, 4.84; N, 5.42; S, 6.19%).

(3c) IR (KBr) : 3356 (N–H), 1747 (C=O), 1586 (C=N), 1424 (C–N), 1233 (C–O), 1073 (C–H def. galactose unit), 784 (C–S), 874 cm⁻¹ (β-isomer of galactose); ¹H NMR δ 7.6–6.9 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.8–6.7 (2H, s, N–H), 5.48 (1H, m, H₁), 5.27–5.08 (1H, m, H₃), 4.80–4.39 (3H, m, H₂, H₄ and H₅), 4.28–4.14 (2H, m, H₆, H_{6'}), 2.1–1.8 (12H, m, 4-OAc group). Mass (*m/z*) 517 (M⁺+1), 474, 331, 229 (Found : C, 48.60; H, 4.60; N, 5.30; S, 6.02. C₂₁H₂₅O₉N₂S requires : C, 48.83; H, 4.84; N, 5.42; S, 6.19%).

(3d) IR (KBr) : 3457 (N–H), 1749 (C=O), 1489 (C=N), 1373 (C–N), 1232 (C–O), 1055 (C–H def. galactose unit), 710 (C–S), 915 cm⁻¹ (β-isomer of galactose); ¹H NMR δ 7.4–6.8 (4H, m, Ar–H), 5.5–5.4 (2H, s, N–H), 5.32–5.07 (2H, m, H₁ and H₃), 4.60–4.21 (2H, m, H₂ and H₄), 4.18–4.12 (2H, m, H₆ and H_{6'}), 4.10–3.90 (1H, m, H₅), 2.1–1.9 (12H, m, 4-OAc group). Mass (*m/z*) 517 (M⁺+1), 441, 331, 229, 169 (Found : C, 48.59; H, 4.58; N, 5.29; S, 6.00. C₂₁H₂₅O₉N₂S requires : C, 48.83; H, 4.84; N, 5.42; S, 6.19%).

(3e) IR (KBr) : 3455 (N–H), 1751 (C=O), 1592 (C=N), 1437 (C–N), 1228 (C–O), 1051 (C–H def. galactose unit), 755 (C–S), 916 cm⁻¹ (β-isomer of galactose) : ¹H NMR δ 7.3–6.9 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.8–6.7 (2H, s, N–H), 5.47 (1H, m, H₁), 5.42–5.34 (2H, m, H₂ and H₃), 4.19–4.12 (2H, m, H₆ and H_{6'}), 4.09–4.05 (1H, m, H₅), 4.23–4.21 (1H, m, H₄), 2.3–1.8 (15H, m, 4-OAc + Ar-CH₃). Mass (*m/z*) 496 (M⁺), 497 (M⁺+1), 421, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 53.01; H, 5.30; N, 5.29; S, 6.15. C₂₂H₂₈O₉N₂S requires : C, 53.22; H, 5.64; N, 5.64; S, 6.45%).

(3f) IR (KBr) : 3386 (N-H), 1749 (C=O), 1592 (C=N), 1436 (C-N), 1231 (C-O), 1054 (C-H def. galactose unit), 743 (C-S), 916 cm^{-1} (β -isomer of galactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 7.3–6.7 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.71–6.67 (1H, s, N-H), 5.47–5.46 (1H, s, N-H), 5.42–5.32 (1H, m, H_1), 5.21–5.08 (2H, m, H_2 and H_3), 4.72–4.56 (1H, m, H_4), 4.15–4.13 (2H, m, H_6 and H_6'), 4.09–4.03 (1H, m, H_5), 2.3–1.9 (15H, m, 4-OAc + Ar- CH_3). Mass (m/z) 497 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 421, 331, 169 (Found : C, 53.05; H, 5.32; N, 5.30; S, 6.25. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 53.22; H, 5.64; N, 5.64; S, 6.45%).

(3g) IR (KBr) : 3454 (N-H), 1751 (C=O), 1509 (C=N), 1434 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1054 (C-H def. galactose unit), 712 (C-S), 915 cm^{-1} (β -isomer of galactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 7.3–6.7 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.45–5.44 (2H, s, N-H), 5.4–5.30 (1H, dd, H_1), 5.19–5.10 (1H, m, H_3), 4.59–4.56 (1H, m, H_4), 4.26–4.21 (1H, m, H_2), 4.16–4.03 (3H, m, H_5 , H_6 and H_6'), 2.3–1.9 (15H, m, 4-OAc + Ar- CH_3). Mass (m/z) 497 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 421, 331, 229, 169 (Found : C, 53.02; H, 5.33; N, 5.38; S, 6.27. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 53.22; H, 5.64; N, 5.64; S, 6.45%).

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